

87. Seedlings were transplanted in 1 row at 18- × 18-cm spacing. Plants were artificially inoculated (clipping method) with a virulent local isolate at maximum tillering. Disease reaction was recorded 20 d after inoculation.

IR22, IR26, IR32, IR36, IR38, and IR42 showed stable resistance, with a narrow reaction range. IR20, IR28, IR29, IR30, and IR34 had a wider reaction range (see table). □

Stability of BB resistance in IR varieties. Hunan, China.

Variety	Test duration	BB reaction ^a	
		Range	Average
IR20	1975-47	1-5	3.15
IR22	1975-87	1-3	2.85
IR26	1975-87	1-3	2.38
IR28	1975-87	1-5	3.30
IR29	1975-47	1-5	3.00
IR30	1975-87	1-5	3.46
IR32	1976-87	1-3	2.67
IR34	1976-47	1-5	3.16
IR36	1976-87	1-3	2.67
IR38	1976-87	1-3	2.67
IR42	1976-87	1-3	2.67

^aStandard evaluation system for rice.

Reaction of rice varieties with xa-5 to four Philippine races of bacterial blight (BB)

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More than 100 varieties having recessive gene xa-5 for BB resistance have been identified (genetic analysis using BB race 1). The xa-5 gene conveys resistance to BB races 1,2, and 3. We have found that varieties with xa-5 give widely variable reaction to race 4.

We reinoculated (clipping method) 6 plants each of 74 varieties with 4 races at maximum tillering. All varieties were resistant to races 1, 2, and 3 (see table). However, 52 were susceptible or moderately susceptible and 22 were resistant or moderately resistant to race 4.

We are analyzing some varieties resistant to race 4 to determine if they

Reaction of rice varieties with xa-5 to 4 Philippine races of BB.

Variety	IRRI acc. no.	Country of origin	Reaction ^a to races			
			1 (PXO 61)	2 (PXO 86)	3 (PXO 79)	4 (PXO 71)
Hashikalmi	3397	Bangladesh	R	R	R	MR
Kele	25881	Bangladesh	R	R	R	MR
Aus 25 1	29043	Bangladesh	R	R	R	MS
Aus 449	29206	Bangladesh	R	R	R	MS
Bageri	16193	Bangladesh	R	R	R	MS
Dharial	3396	Bangladesh	R	R	R	MS
DV29	8816	Bangladesh	R	R	R	MR
DV319	8880	Bangladesh	R	R	R	R
DD100	8649	Bangladesh	MR	MR	MR	MS
DNJ 142	8426	Bangladesh	R	R	R	MS
DV32	8818	Bangladesh	R	R	R	MR
DV52	8828	Bangladesh	R	R	R	MR
DV85	8839	Bangladesh	R	R	R	R
DV86	8840	Bangladesh	R	R	R	R
DZ78	8555	Bangladesh	R	R	R	MS
Pankhiraj	24139	Bangladesh	R	R	R	MS
Dharial	34034	Bangladesh	R	R	R	MR
UCP 28	8728	Bangladesh	R	R	R	MS
Laksmijota	31595	Bangladesh	R	R	R	MS
Lahargura	25886	Bangladesh	R	R	R	MS
Loroi	27567	Bangladesh	R	R	R	R
Chinsurah Boro II	11484	India	R	R	R	R
Koalarata	28598	India	R	R	R	MR
ARC6231	12260	India	R	R	R	MS
ARC6565	20400	India	R	R	R	S
ARC7001	20436	India	MR	R	R	S
ARC7013	20437	India	R	R	R	MS
ARC7043	20458	India	R	R	R	MS
ARC7045	20460	India	R	R	R	S
ARC7046	20461	India	R	R	R	S
ARC7055	20468	India	R	R	R	S
ARC7060	20471	India	R	R	R	MS
ARC7090	20490	India	R	R	R	S
ARC7098	20498	India	R	R	R	MR
ARC7102	20501	India	R	R	R	MS
ARC7128	20524	India	R	R	R	MS
ARC7207	20545	India	R	R	R	S
ARC7260	12346	India	R	R	R	S
ARC7291	12356	India	R	R	R	MS
ARC7323	20602	India	R	R	R	MS
ARC7336	20606	India	R	R	R	MS
ARC7406	20617	India	R	R	R	MS
ARC7416	20625	India	R	R	R	MS
ARC7423	20627	India	R	R	R	MS
ARC10027	20655	India	R	R	R	MS
ARC10376	20887	India	R	R	R	MR
ARC10520	20967	India	R	R	R	MR
ARC10952	12682	India	R	R	R	MS
ARC11067	42623	India	R	R	R	MR
ARC11071	21184	India	R	R	R	MR
ARC11072	21186	India	R	R	R	MS
ARC11075	21188	India	R	R	R	S
ARC11083	21189	India	R	R	R	MR
ARC11092	21192	India	R	R	R	MS
ARC11109	21199	India	R	R	R	MR
ARC11121	21207	India	R	R	R	MR
ARC11204	21223	India	R	R	R	MR
ARC11219	21236	India	R	R	R	MR
BJI	3711	Nepal	R	R	R	R
Banglaluwa	16268	Nepal	R	R	R	MS
Devarasi	16173	Nepal	R	R	R	MS
Dudhi	16256	Nepal	R	R	R	MS
Lal Ahu	16121	Nepal	R	R	R	MS
Lalaka Gadur	16255	Nepal	R	R	R	S
Lal Sar	16185	Nepal	R	R	R	MS
Matury	16190	Nepal	R	R	R	S
Nakhi	16254	Nepal	R	R	R	S
Ram Bilash	16273	Nepal	R	R	R	MS

Continued on next page

Table continued

Variety	IRRI acc. no.	Country of origin	Reaction ^a to races			
			1 (PXO 61)	2 (PXO 86)	3 (PXO 79)	4 (Pxo 71)
Sajani	16177	Nepal	R	R	R	S
Sokan Dhan	16250	Nepal	R	R	R	MS
Tally	16146	Nepal	R	R	R	MR
Gokhue Sair	16195	Nepal	R	R	R	MS
Mujaer	18296	Indonesia	R	R	R	MS
DL 5	8593	Pakistan	R	R	R	MS

^a R = resistant, MR = moderately resistant, MS = moderately susceptible, S = susceptible.

have an additional gene for resistance.

A vast majority of the varieties came from gene center 1, comprising Bangladesh, Nepal, and northeast India. One variety is from Indonesia and one from Pakistan. □

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Reaction of IR varieties to tungro (RTV) in the Philippines

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IR varieties were tested for reaction to RTV during the 1986 dry season in Koronadal, South Cotabato; Baybay, Leyte; and Guimba, Nueva Ecija. Disease incidence was based on symptoms; rice tungro bacilliform virus (RTBV) and rice tungro spherical virus (RTSV) in rice plants were indexed by the latex test 60 d after transplanting. Symptoms of RTV incidence in fields surrounding the test sites were assessed visually.

RTV incidence varied among varieties and locations (see table). In Nueva Ecija, where virtually no RTV incidence

was observed in the surrounding fields, only RTSV infection occurred in all varieties. In Leyte, where RTV incidence was moderately low, high levels of RTSV infection and low levels of RTBV infection occurred in all varieties. In South Cotabato, where RTV incidence was high, many varieties were infected with both viruses.

Even under high disease pressure in South Cotabato, IR56, IR60, and IR62 had relatively low infection rates. IR50, IR54, and IR64, which have Gam Pai 30-12-15 as a donor for vector resistance in their parentage, showed low infection rates with either virus in Nueva Ecija but high infection rates in Leyte and South Cotabato. IR26 and IR30 were mostly infected with RTBV alone in South Cotabato.

These results indicate field resistance to RTV in IR50, IR54, and IR64 in Nueva Ecija but not in Leyte and South Cotabato.

The latex test on test plants and plants from surrounding fields in South Cotabato revealed 12% infection with rice grassy stunt virus (GSV). It seemed that GSV strain 2, which caused RTV-like symptoms, was prevalent in South Cotabato. GSV-infected plants might have been scored RTV-infected.

These results confirm that RTV incidence varies with disease severity and the vector population prevailing in the area. Unsuspected RTSV occurs widely in fields perceived to be disease-free. □

Ketoacids in healthy and bacterial blight (BB)-affected leaves of susceptible and tolerant rice varieties

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Ketoacids act as precursors of amino acids. Their alteration may affect the composition of amino acids during disease development in rice leaves.

Three ketoacids — pyruvic acid, α -ketoglutaric acid, and an unknown ketoacid — were detected in healthy and inoculated plants of susceptible TN1 and tolerant IET4141 rice varieties. Their content during disease development in inoculated leaves of both varieties was greater than in healthy leaves. Disease stages 1 to 5 were monitored at 2, 5, 10, 15, and 20 d after inoculation of 55-d-old rice plants with a virulent isolate of *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae*.

RTV incidence based on symptoms, and RTBV and RTSV infection based on the latex test in IR varieties 60 d after transplanting in fields in Nueva Ecija, Leyte, and South Cotabato, Philippines.

Variety	Nueva Ecija ^a		Leyte			South Cotabato			
	RTSV infection (%)	RTV incidence (%)	Infection (%)			RTV incidence (%)	Infection (%)		
			RTBV+ RTSV	RTBV	RTSV		RTBV+ RTSV	RTBV	RTSV
IR22	11	61	20	13	11	99	50	8	29
IR26	12	0	0	2	0	89	0	34	0
IR30	10	0	0	1	0	49	2	37	1
IR36	29	5	4	3	22	92	19	12	19
IR42	26	25	17	4	64	98	25	14	20
IR50	9	1	2	2	28	100	39	10	19
IR54	4	3	4	2	48	100	65	5	21
IR56	5	0	0	1	2	5	1	2	10
IR60	26	0	0	1	4	29	1	3	11
IR62	13	0	0	0	4	7	4	2	25
IR64	6	3	2	2	28	100	31	15	22

^a No visual scoring made. No RTBV+RTSV or RTBV infection observed.